

The Role Of Education On Economic Development

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Abstract

Since the birth of industrialization and nation-states, education has been seen as a power and a vehicle which shapes society and people, also it provides economic and social development. Well-educated people in society are seen as more successful and productive. Societies which have power of trained people become advanced societies. For this purpose, education is seen as the most important and profitable investment tool for the people and the country's future. One of the most important factors that influence the development level of economy, society and policy is education. Today people can easily relate economic development with level of education. The thought of the more people are educated, the more they contribute to the society spreads. Education is the basis of economical development. The purpose of the education is to meet the requirements of both the country and the people. Rapid change of production technologies caused the importance of the education increase. As a result, need of investing in information emerged.

Keywords: Education, Development,

INTRODUCTION

Education, in the behavior of individuals through their lives were like deliberately bring about change is a process. To equip people with the desired behavior, ie to train throughout the ages has been the most important goal. Today, this phenomenon come to increasingly complex situations and the impact is being felt even more intensely. In addition to this the importance of education, especially in our country are poorly understood . However, in the direction of human behavior without the development of a reliable and valid, longed to achieve a lifestyle is not the case. The most concrete and lean human relations, in the most abstract and complex relationships of all kinds can be nested process. States will manage the factories to plan, to build, to operate our products, to distribute, to consume nature to handle , her products will nest to build schools, roads, dams will do, or all of them will eliminate, objects and phenomena related issues will take, or emerging It is the people who will solve the problems. As such, people with consistent behavior, so we have to equip them with knowledge and skills in problem solving. This can be achieved by education. [2]

1.The Necessity Of Education And Training

Investing in people essentially covers three areas. These are education, health and nutrition is. These three areas of expenditure carried out in a balanced manner in the case of human resources, as needed, it is possible to take advantage of. However, we also need to remember that investing in people spending on education constitutes the foundation. Education investments not only in terms of the least developed countries, but also in terms of the advanced industrial

countries is an issue that should be emphasized. Investigating the cause of the development of the advanced industrial countries, according to some economists, this is one of the reasons why the rapid development of industry in the country, in excess of 2% of GDP in these countries as a part of the continuous education and research spending is the separation. [9]

Education, individuals from birth to death is an ongoing phenomenon and the political, social, cultural and individual dimensions simultaneously in possession, because it is a concept that is difficult to be identified. Society's standards, beliefs and ways of life are critical in all social processes. People who lived in the community value, aptitude, attitude and behavior of all of the processes are developed. Selected and controlled environment (especially school) under the influence of social competence and optimum individual development is a social process that enables. Education, according to a predetermined based on people's attitudes affect certain developments planned for providing system free. Education, in the behavior of individuals through their life is a process of deliberately wanted to bring about change. [11]

Training people on the one hand while giving information to produce knowledge on the one hand, gives you the ability to understand and interpret. Training given to members of the community, is an investment in human capital because they are more productive through training people for life. Education is an investment made on human beings are different from other investments. Strong and respected country in the international arena today being the most important measure, showing a healthy and stable development of the economy. That, in providing the resources of the country with active participation of

human capital in the production process is of great importance. Compatible monitoring of employment and vocational training policies, parallel to the labor needs of the economy in sufficient number and quality of labor force training is necessary in this regard. Today, in developed economies, sophistication, one of the most important factors determining the measure is the priority given to education services. Supply of educational services to the cause of so much importance, to be held in appropriate conditions of this service resulting in significant social benefits and positive externalities community spread. [12]

In our century, all roads; education out of the economic life can be better equipped to deal with the problems encountered and the information is not been in prison. Information is needed to give direction to individuals is an information cage. It is for the last quarter century, our world, a dizzying rapidly advancing technology on the scene back not want to stay nations, cure investing in education, the information systems and technology developments in the parallel educational programs of the era as needed regulates found . A country's economic development, of that country 's people, said to be due to personal and social development. Developed through education and appropriate social behavior to target the use of new values, is extremely important in terms of economic development to accelerate. Ley to the building, development is not just about material needs, people are also concerned with the development of social conditions. Investing in people essentially covers three areas. These are education, health and nutrition is. These three areas of expenditure carried out in a balanced manner in the case of human resources, as needed, it is possible to take advantage of. However, we also need to remember that investing in people spending on education constitutes the foundation. [13]

Education investments not only in terms of the least developed countries, but also in terms of the advanced industrial countries is an issue that should be emphasized. Investigating the cause of the development of the advanced industrial countries, according to some economists, this is one reason why the rapid development of industry in the country, in this country, of GDP in excess of 2% as a part of education and research spending is the separation constant. A matter of importance should be underlined why the system input-output relationship with the environment are constantly interacting. Pioneering work on this subject contained in the system according to Katz and Kahn's clear understanding of the system receives inputs from the outside to the external environment by producing process and provides something new. As a result of this sequence of operations in light of feedback from the external environment they fix themselves are changing

purposes. The most important of which is today essentially a system entry, human resources, respectively. People's organizations before joining the organization after joining the accumulation and development here are regarded as a factor that increases the productivity of the organization. After all, qualified human, are the most fundamental elements to improve the efficiency of the organization. From this perspective the economic development of a country when that country's people, said to be due to personal and social development. Developed through education and social behaviors to target the use of appropriate new value criteria, in terms of economic development is extremely important to accelerate. Development is not only about material needs, people are also concerned with the social conditions improved. Improve the quality of the product, especially to increase productivity by improving education, economic and social development could significantly contribute to awareness of the fact that our country has started to become more sensitive about investing in people. [13]

2.Social and Economic Benefits of Education

Education, training areas, as well as quality of life and the environment at the same time improves the quality of life in society. Therefore, our young enough to get a good education and social welfare is one of the most effective ways of providing increased. Good education will primarily benefit them, because it increases efficiency and effectiveness. Generally a good business education in the arms of their work is attractive working environment. Therefore, the quality of work environment they affect quality of life. Nowadays working life undoubtedly become educated and become successful is founded on. For this success to capture people in a way, an upper class (in terms of career and salary) they need to rise heavily in education and a large portion of resources to spend on education began. Indeed, nowadays the number of state universities and private universities for the number of 53 to 23 were found. Turkey's largest 400 private sector companies and the results of his research seems to confirm this phenomenon. Thus in our country close to 97% of company managers department, bachelor, master, doctoral taken, consists of managers get 3% has been observed that undergraduate education. In the study mentioned, also, that with career development, organization development managers themselves, the better educated, with more training and attend seminars positive correlation between the success of organizations that have determined. New century is, continuing education, productivity and quality century, we must emphasized this. Education brought almost

like a gold chain process efficiency, quality and employment on the one hand with the development of Turkey, competitiveness, while helping to enrichment through expanding employment on the other hand extending to the richness of our time is your turn. In this new world of freedom with the fearless society, humane working conditions are to bring. Indeed directed to the information age in a global economy, growth and employment problems, solutions will be brought, as a strategic factor in continuing education takes place in our country's development level, cultural structure of graduates empowered to solve problems and provide services to the community as a total capacity is an indicator of the quality of our education system. Where if you keep hold of him today from start to finish with every aspect of our education system unplanned, unscheduled, who does not know what to look for in a structure. The natural result of this, the output of the system in the same way that graduates are making plans and programs take a leading role in society and contribute to the production on their own do not offer. Each year they receive a hundred thousand graduates as a reflection of rote learning and the ability to produce healthy thinking they can not exhibit their shows. These are the reasons that professional knowledge in society and social profiles is very low. Çukurova University faculty members in their research is done just young people looking at things in college , problem solving, change of trend perspective with which they come in almost universities are graduating. The best way of manpower and training from primary school to university cultivating all formal and non-formal education opportunities that use the result of a process is realized. Turkish education system at primary level, good people educated good citizens when targeting primary school given over to secondary and higher education, the good citizenship qualifications, support and people to life to prepare his life to execute and in the community, productive and respected as an individual experience will enable to have an occupation aimed. World economy integration efforts are in Turkey and developed countries of the place it deserves to receive developing technology to track it, producing goods and services to reflect the technology of producing and selling a country to rise is required. For this it is necessary to have a qualified workforce. Investment in education is one of the most important goals of education spending to compete in international markets is to produce qualified workforce. This occurs through investments and expenditures of a country's labor force that can be used for the measurement of human capital stock is one of the most realistic display. To examine the relationship between education and economic growth in a model study of the educational level of the labor force or employment are the most important

indicators. As of 1999, the workforce aged 25-64 in OECD countries on average 31 percent lower levels of education in primary schools and for our country , while this ratio is 73 percent owner . In OECD countries aged 25-64 and 42 per cent of the labor force with secondary education level, while this ratio is 16 percent for our country . High school level educated workforce, while 24 percent of OECD countries, Turkey 25-64 the tertiary level educated workforce is only 11 percent of the total workforce. In 1999 "Household Labour Force Survey" Looking at the results of Turkey's population is quite low in terms of education we see. To give an example with numbers Turkey also of the civilian population age 12 and above only 85,7% are literate. Read-author of the proportion of primary school graduates 55 % of women and 13% of the secondary school and vocational school graduates. These figures show that Turkey should give more importance to education in the country. We can provide our employees with the skills and the quality of education because employees can improve their existing qualifications; increasing employee motivation can raise productivity and quality. Knowledge and knowledgeable people of the economy, the most important input has become today, the population's education level at least average in OECD countries closer to a non Turkey's young and dynamic population development driving force of the making is not possible. Turkey in front of omission in education development has attracted the set with his hands. Canceled due to lack of resources the opinion of the investment needed in education, history of emotional investment, which, in other words, who is responsible for the occurrence of these results the defense does not mean anything other than that . Because making the necessary investments in education, not resources is a matter of preference. Instead of the state in Turkey for many years people have chosen to invest in other sectors. Today, investments in other sectors that can operate efficiently with a skilled work force, because there was a huge economic losses are confronted with. Well educated to take care of their health than they are less affected by stress because of the easier solutions to the problems they are observed. Members of the community to better education in basic health indicators is the fact that better. Notable among education and health education of family members in other matters related to their own health as well as the health of children in particular is causing the positive developments. In addition to these health-related education can be described as secondary effects must also be mentioned. They won because the training is based on positive habits. Research on individuals who smoke an additional 1.6 years of training daily cigarette consumption in men, women revealed that the decrease

1.1. Again, additional training in a similar way that the weekly exercises increase an average of 17 minutes yielded the results. [6]

Education Another positive effect of the individual and public health as well, due to increasing health expenditure per capita income remains the same, even if this ratio is now being referred to a larger figure . In addition, the positive developments in the individual and the public health workforce can make positive contributions to productivity. By the OECD for three different countries as a result of work done by applying three different scenarios with the education of the individual and public health is possible to observe these relationships. Research training in a 2 percent increase in spending which will be held, the life expectancy at birth of 25.1 years in France, England 1-year increase of 1.5 indicates that in the USA. Education level is no longer in the community of innovation and technology adoption rates increase. Therefore, education level, which is necessary for development and value-added investments in R & D helps to increase. In order to provide better quality of education in the use of technology in the educational process is inevitable. This is to ensure the use of technology that can produce a system that can adapt it to various processes are needed. The creation of the system in question is largely devoted to Research and Development activities is associated with economic resources. However, in this regard, Turkey has found in the table is not at all positive indicators. Research and development spending by 1 percent for the classification of information and technology producing countries usually located under the information society is considered a country could not be. State Institute Of Statistics (SIS) have done the research and development expenditure in Turkey according to the survey, 80 percent contribution to the state of the industry, there are around 20 per cent contribution. In industrialized countries, the private sector spends on research and development activities in Turkey, on the contrary, are so much above hand. World technology to acquire, learn to assimilate, economy related activities or areas of the become used to this technology, a high-level reproduce the ability to win and the skill of technology as a source of science producing capability of winning deepen to this process, as a whole, on a regular and systematic basis over the will make it possible to sat. An education-training system development and it is integrated, the private sector and the public sector R & D institutions and universities will get into the national R & D network to establish priority be given , education reform, the main axis will create. The effect of education to economic growth is now indisputable position. But nowadays Education-Economics connection is still not adequate. Do not invest enough in education. So in our age the

country's investment in education has become the most valuable investment for the future. This feature of education than others to realize the country has made great improvements. Now, without investing in education, competitive advantage in international markets to improve the welfare of society aside, even with countries that invest in training will not be easy to become equal. Today, the physical size measurement, such as measuring the amount of development rather than knowledge-based values have been started . Industry in the establishment, in renewed for the operation of the new technology has gained strategic importance due to the measures. Therefore obtain these technologies, which is produced in the economy of the country come to stop the country's integrity and security is extremely important in terms of. The purpose of the educational community economic development and social progress is increasing the impact of science and technology. To increase the prosperity of our people and to improve the quality of life can be achieved by training is given due attention. This can only be achieved by trained brain. The most important investment is the investment in trained people. Generating economic growth and prosperity but the technology can increase our level. That science, technology, R & D and trained brain power we can achieve by giving due importance. [6]

3.Means of Economic Development

Development, aims to improve the welfare of individuals with levels of political power by following certain economic policies, is an attempt to change the structure of society. This aspect of the development, both economic and social process. Many many young people, and an economy that is developing in accordance with the constitutional goal of cultivating educational , social, cultural and psychological effects of the economic impact as well as indicates. [1]

Development, growth in the economy as well as social and cultural factors in the development of the means to be. So the development of quantitative indicators, as well as literacy rate, birth rate, life expectancy and non-numerical indicators as well get into it. Development is usually used for less developed countries is a concept. [10]

Development, but also the welfare of individuals with the aim to increase levels of political power by following certain economic policies, is an attempt to change the structure of society. [7]

Development system is based on a completely new technology. Technological advances from one side production and increasing trade of the capitalist system led to the evolution , as in the 1930s, Schumpeter's workers increased well being thus capitalism will collapse prediction in a similar way, developed the

automation system and human production and the world of work outside the throwing their doom is like. Although the use of technology is increasingly simple, the technology for production and development scientists and R & D studies are needed. In need of R & D work in the use of both traditional and current technology still plays a pivotal role human. In fact, development is for man, and hence economic growth, human rights, community of people, a healthy environment, prosperity, equitable income distribution is not supported by such factors do not mean anything. [5]

We can list the following characteristics of developing countries;

- a. Income levels are low and inequitable dispersion of
- b. The weight of the agricultural sector of the economy is more than
- c. The lack of industry sector
- d. The lack of competitiveness in foreign trade
- e. Low levels of business scale
- f. Saving level is low
- g. Migration and urbanization problems to be
- h. Have low levels of education and health standards [4]

The good functioning of the economy and easier dissemination of advanced technologies to ensure externalities are important in terms of education. Based market economy, and it increases the level of education of individuals begin to function better. The higher the level of education of individuals is easier to adapt to technical change. One of the most important external benefits of education to the better functioning of democratic institutions that allow an informed society is developed. Higher level of education of individuals in society is democratic institutions handle better. Create a well-trained people in the community being extremely low crime rate, that spending on internal security and justice services leads to a reduction in. Increasing the level of education of the poor, the cut-off income level began to rise and transfers to the poor expenditures (food, health and education assistance, unemployment benefits, etc.) is decreasing. People's incomes rising rapidly increasing level of education, number of people in need of social assistance is declining. Educated people in health care are more aware and cautious. Earning capacity of individuals with education in parallel with the increase in capacity is also increasing tax payments. Therefore, the total tax revenue raised education spending is done. [8]

4. Education and Economic Development

Of developing countries in the economic development of 4-5 basic steps are: First, work-intensive production, and second, mimicking the simple technology of developed countries, older machines taking the

production, making it the third phase of heavy industry, technology heads intimidation and small innovations, the fourth stage of formal R & D, scientific process compliance, new product development and electronic development and end-stage intense R & D efforts, science, basic research and new discoveries increase is seen. 1960's years of the great powers from industrialized countries to developing countries to transfer information opened the doors is the period; ago take labor from foreign countries, and then starting to establish production facilities in developing countries. Information from these years, production increase and begin to play an important role in the quality of the period began. Not enough to just one training in education, according to changing business and market conditions, people started to train again and again. [5]

In the development of the country, the size of the accumulation of physical capital, human capital factors as the nature of the impact is too great. As known, one of the variables that determine the quality of human capital is education. Education of the countries they have on economic development by improving the quality of human capital contribute significantly. [3]

The welfare of the country has a linear relationship with levels of economic development. Underdeveloped or underdeveloped countries, one of the major problems is the problem of education. Lack of education services in developing countries, economic development is regarded as one of the obstacles. Indicators of development of a country's level of education, there is a special place and importance. When we look at the developed countries, leaving more resources for education services, training, and the longer the duration of the training is observed to be more qualified. School education not only in developed countries, to meet the demands of different types and levels of education, there are institutions. Depending on lifelong learning approach in all age levels, from psychology to art education, sports, hobbies claimed to education for all types of education provided by the private sector to participate in courses where possible. These types of courses, can be given in almost all cities and costs can be met by anyone with an average level of earnings. The establishment of democracy, political stability, ensuring cultural development, the relative reduction in crime rates, tolerance, such as the formation of a healthy society, the basic variables in determining the level of education, emerges as a key factor. To accept the rule of law and to implement certain educational level of citizens should not have. The necessity of education for the independence of the judiciary is clearly seen. Formation of democratic institutions, democratic rule processing, but certain educational levels of society can be given effect by. For this reason, physical and financial capital

equipment in a country's development, next to the level of human capital endowments also plays a determining role. [6]

5. Concluding Remarks

Going back to Adam Smith, economists for a long time the importance of education, economic development and tried to measure the positive contribution. Despite these efforts a long time, with the economic development of the employee number is assumed to depend on the amount of physical capital. In the knowledge and skills of the workforce, due to the increases in productivity and improvements, economic development and can contribute to an increase in national wealth is considered. However after World War II, studies of manpower resources to the economic development of positive change will occur at a greater rate than all the other elements that contribute revealed. [7]

Development of the investments to be made only with the provision of the physical means of production is impossible. On the human element or manpower resources for the development of the social and structural change in the investment accelerator and the effects are very important to

raise the level of production. Education is the leading force in economic development, well-trained manpower (human capital) are developing countries with faster. Japan and Germany are the best examples of this. Education of the public peace and order, but also in the development of society and civilization and plays an important role in ensuring economic development. To break the vicious cycle of poverty, raise the level of education is a requirement to supply. Very close relationship between education and development is concerned, economic development can not be performed without training. [5]

Education, quick and a steady increase in income leads to the population of the nature and way of life as it affects the investment priorities of the education is necessary to separate the traditional education system, science and technology rapid development, socio-economic globalization and the use of computers, the transformation of society and age with the change would have lost value. Training to individuals to adapt to environmental changes occurring in the new behavior is obliged to provide. This obligation of the education system to fulfill the rapidly changing information and technology to adapt to a accessing characteristics is obtained. People, and to adapt to changes in the environment as well as to provide training to reach proficiency will create a change task when the education system is in a constant change and renewal is required. Today, the purpose of education only to raise literacy can not stay, but also creative, energetic, think globally and act locally. The entrepreneur must be able to train people. Therefore

training The purpose of the concept of a comprehensive resource for education reform for allocation and plans must be prepared and implemented. This plan into practice support of the people and the plan can be put into an inevitable necessity to understand respectively. However, industry, civil society organizations, the media, school management and teachers must show a positive attitude to it.

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